

THE BEST WAYS OF LEARNING PHRASAL VERBS

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Abstract:

This article focuses on phrasal verbs how to make, use them and learn correctly in English context.

Keywords: phrasal verbs, transitive, intransitive, separable, inseparable, multi-words, practice.

Nowadays, we are witnessing that the globe is developing day by day. Therefore, learning foreign language is important aspect of life, actually English language. Knowing English is very common around the globe. One of the most essential decision that result in good changes, especially in foreign language. Resolution No PQ – 5112 dated 19.05.2021 “On measure to bring the activities of popularization of learning languages in the Republic of Uzbekistan to a qualitatively new level was signed by the president [2].

In recent years, most people are learning English. Not knowing English is strange in nowadays. So, learning any languages is a long way. This way will be boring because a language includes in different parts. For example, Phrasal Verbs in English is a bit of difficult rather than another part. What is Phrasal Verbs?

Phrasal Verb is a standard verb, such as put, go, take, plus one or two particles.

What is particle in phrasal verb? Particle is a preposition or adverbs such as: go after, go out. After and out prepositions.

Go together and go away-together and away are adverbs. Another examples of phrasal verbs: hang out, look after, put away, hung up, bring out. Phrasal verbs are transitive and intransitive. A transitive phrasal verb takes an object, for examples: Hang up your jacket. I look up to your dad. Intransitive phrasal verbs are easier to use because there is no object to worry about. Here are some examples of intransitive phrasal verbs [1:50].

She grew up in UK. The plane took off and landed on time. Your children are growing up so fast. What do you want to be when you grow up? One important distinction between phrasal verbs is that they are separable or separable. Separable phrasal verbs have a particle that can be separable from the base verb and moved to different positions within the sentence. Examples of separable phrasal verbs. Take on – to become responsible for, For example: I am going to take on the project. I am going to the project on. Inseparable phrasal verbs have particular that can not be separated from the base verb. Such as: look up to: To look (someone)up to, to look up (someone)to is not correct in context. I really look up to my mum. She looks after her sister. He stands up for yourself. It is important to know that some phrasal verbs can be separable and inseparable depending on context .For instance ,take your shoes off in separable context.

The plane is about to take off is inseparable in context as an object is not required.(3)

Phrasal verbs are multi-word verbs. Some examples for this. I give up! It is too hard. He always gives up without really trying. We are not giving up yet! In this context, Phrasal Verbs change by tenses. How to learn phrasal verbs easily?

First, you need to know the meaning of the whole phrasal verb. Useful tips for learning phrasal verbs.

1.Don't group them by verb. To group the phrasal verbs by a particular verb, get up, get over, get through, get back at.

2.Group them by particle. Each phrasal verb is composed of a verb and a particle.

3.Group them by topic.

Better way to learn phrasal verbs is to organize them by subject. For example, you should make a phrasal verb list for expressing emotion, describing friends, talking about love and relationship.

4.Find the right phrasal verbs to practice. There are a lot of phrasal verb but you should not learn them. You should learn only them that you need to learn.

5.Practise using phrasal verb

Another effective way to practice phrasal verb is create a story with them. If you like writing fiction, you can create a short story using a few phrasal verbs. This method will help you create connection between the words you learnt.

In conclusion, there is no magic way learning phrasal verbs. It requires time, patience and stability. If you are going to be confident in speaking, you should know phrasal verbs and practice them Phrasal verbs are ubiquitous in spoken language, understanding them allow for easier grasp of conversation.

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